

Original article

Prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates from children with diarrhoea in Maiduguri, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: *Campylobacter* species are recognised as leading causes of bacterial associated gastroenteritis in children. It is associated with a concerning trend of emergence of resistance to commonly used antibiotics for the treatment of the infections. **Objective:** This study investigated the prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of *C. jejuni* isolates from diarrhoeic stool samples of under 5 years old children, who presented with diarrhoea in Maiduguri, Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** Stool samples were collected from 245 children with diarrhoea and 100 children without diarrhoea. *C. jejuni* was isolated using standard microbiological techniques and confirmed with a conventional polymerase chain reaction assay. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed on the isolates using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method recommended by Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). **Results:** The prevalence of *Campylobacter* was 21.6% (53/245) in children with diarrhoea and 5% (5/100) in children without diarrhoea. Among the cases, the prevalence was highest in children below 2 years of age and lowest in 5-year-old children, with a higher infection rate in males than females (17.6 vs. 11.8%). The results of antibiotic susceptibility testing showed high resistance of the isolates to ampicillin, tetracycline, and ciprofloxacin. However, the isolates were susceptible to gentamicin, azithromycin, and chloramphenicol. Simultaneous resistance to three or more antibiotics (Multiresistance) was detected in 48/53 (90.5%) isolates. **Conclusion:** This study demonstrates a high prevalence of *Campylobacter jejuni* diarrhoea, with an alarming resistance to key antibiotics commonly used for treating *Campylobacter* infections in Maiduguri, Nigeria. Clinicians must suspect *Campylobacter* in paediatric patients presenting with diarrhoea in Maiduguri health facilities.

Keywords: Antibiotic *Campylobacter*, Children, Diarrhoea, Maiduguri, Prevalence, Resistance.

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Introduction

Campylobacter species are recognised as leading causes of bacterial gastroenteritis worldwide, with *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* being the most common species of the pathogen associated with human disease with varying prevalence rates worldwide.^{1,2,21} Other species of *Campylobacter* such as *C. fetus*, *C. upsaliensis*, *C. lari* and *C. hyointestinalis*, have also been implicated in human infections.¹ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), *Campylobacter* causes an estimated 400-500 million cases of diarrhoea yearly (WHO 2019). In Africa, *Campylobacter* infections is an important public health concern, particularly in children under the age of five.¹ In Nigeria a study conducted in the northcentral region reported a

prevalence of 8.7% in paediatric patients.¹⁸ Consumption of contaminated food, water, unpasteurized dairy products, contact with infected animals, and poor hygiene practices have been reported as major risk factors for *Campylobacter jejuni*-induced childhood diarrhoea.^{1,6} The emergence and spread of antibiotic-resistant *Campylobacter* in human infection is serious a public health challenge, as it can lead to treatment failure and increased risk of post-infection complications.³ Despite the growing concern on antibiotic resistance among *Campylobacter* strains, there is a dearth of data on the prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of *C. jejuni* isolates from children with diarrhoea in the studied area and the country at large. The current study aimed to bridge this knowledge gap by investigating the prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of isolates of *C. jejuni* from diarrhoeic children in Maiduguri, northeastern Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in Maiduguri Metropolis, the capital city of Borno State in northeastern Nigeria. The tropical climate and high temperatures of Maiduguri create an ideal environment for the growth and transmission of *Campylobacter*. The suitability of Maiduguri for this study is further enhanced by its high population of children and its being a major hub for livestock and poultry farming and trading in northeastern Nigeria.

Study design

The study employed a cross-sectional design to investigate the prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of *C. jejuni* isolates from children with diarrhoea in Maiduguri, Nigeria from June 2018 to December 2019.

Study Population

The study population consisted of under 5-year-old, ranging from 0-59 months, with diarrhoea (\geq loose stools in 24 hours) and children without diarrhoea attending paediatric out-patient unit at the State Specialist Hospital (SSH) and the Nursing Home (NH). Studying out patients can provide community-based perspective on *Campylobacter* infections, which can inform public health interventions.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Children aged 0-59 months who presented with acute diarrhoea at the Paediatric Unit of the State Specialist Hospital and the Nursing Home and

children whose parents consented to participate were included in the study. Children with diarrhoea receiving antibiotics within the past 2 weeks, and children whose parents declined to enroll were excluded from the study.

Sample Size determination

The sample size was calculated applying the formula $n = Z^2 p(1-p)/E^2$ (20), where n is sample size, Z is the Z-score p is the estimated prevalence, and E is the desired margin of error. At a desired confidence level of 95%, with a margin of error of 5%, and an estimated prevalence of 20%, we estimated the sample size as 245.

Sampling Techniques

The convenience sampling method was used to enroll children presenting with diarrhoea and children without diarrhoea (control) over a period of 12 months, aimed at recruiting 25 children per month.

Sample size

A total of 245 children presenting with diarrhoea and 100 children without diarrhoea were enrolled in the study.

Sample Collection

Stool samples were collected from under 5-year-old children with diarrhoea and without diarrhoea, stored in sterile containers, and transported to the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) Medical Microbiology laboratory within 2 hours in ice packs, and processed immediately for isolation and identification of *Campylobacter* using standard microbiological techniques.

Isolation and Identification of *Campylobacter jejuni*

One gram/1ml of stool sample was added to 9 mL *Campylobacter* enrichment broth (LAB M Ltd, UK) with cefoperazone, vancomycin, trimethoprim and natamycin (LAB M Ltd, UK), The mixture was vortexed and incubated at 42°C for 48 h under microaerophilic atmosphere (12% CO₂, 3% H₂, 11% O₂, 74% N₂) provided using GENbag microaer (BioMérieux, Etoile-France). After enrichment 100 μ l was plated onto *Campylobacter* selective agar plates (IDG Ltd, UK) containing cefoperazone and vancomycin and incubated at 42°C for 60 – 72 hours under microaerophilic condition as above and examined at intervals of 24 h, 48 h and 72 hours. Suspected colonies were subcultured on blood agar plates and incubated at 42°C for 24 hours under microaerophilic conditions. The inoculated plates were examined for typical *Campylobacter* colonies (small, gray, and flat with a smooth edge). Isolates were confirmed as *Campylobacter* species using Gram staining reaction as well as oxidase and catalase tests. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

amplification of the *Hip O* gene was performed as described by On *et al.*¹⁶ to confirm the identification of *Campylobacter jejuni*

DNA extraction

Genomic nucleic acid extraction was performed using the phenol-chloroform method previously described.¹⁶ Five *Campylobacter* colonies from blood agar were placed in a 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube containing 400 µl lysis buffer and 10 µl proteinase K and incubated at 56°C for 1 hour and vortexed at every 20-minute interval. The supernatant was discarded and the pellets mixed with 400 µl of phenol-chloroform, was vortexed, and spun at 14000g for 10 min. The supernatant was removed and mixed with 400 µl of chloroform, shaken using vortex, and centrifuged at high speed as above. The lysate was mixed with equal volumes of 3 M sodium acetate and 100% cold ethanol and then incubated at 20°C for 24 hours. Following incubation, the mixture was spun at 14000 rpm for 10 minutes in cold centrifuge. The upper layer was removed, and 200 µl of 70% alcohol was added to the pellets and centrifuged at 14000 rpm for 4 minutes at 4°C. Finally, the upper layer was discarded, and DNA pellets were dried at room temperature and then re-suspended in 30 µl of sterile water.

Polymerase chain reaction

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for confirmation of *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates initially identified using cultural isolation and biochemical tests methods was performed as at DNA Laboratory in Kaduna, Nigeria. The *Hip O* gene of *C. jejuni* was targeted using the primers Forward 5' GAA-GAG-GGT-TTG-GGT-GGT-G-3' and Reverse 5' RAG-CGC-TTC-GCA-TAA-CTT-G-3'. The polymerase chain reaction was performed in a final volume of 20 µl containing 2x Tag premix PCR mastermix (Bioneer, Korea), 1 µl of forward (F) primer, 1µl of reverse(R) primer, 2 µl of template DNA, and 14µl deionized water. The amplification conditions were initial denaturation for 3 min at 96 °C, followed by 35 cycles of 96 °C for 30s, 55 °C for 30s, and 72 °C for 30s and a final extension of 72 °C for 5 min in a programmable thermal cycler (PTC-100 Peltier; MJ Research, California, USA). Subsequently, 5µl of each amplification product mixed with 1µl of 6x DNA loading dye (Bioneer, Korea) was subjected to electrophoresis using 1.5% (w/v) agarose gel stained with 1µg/ml Ethidium bromide. A 100 bp molecular size marker (Bioneer, Korea) was run concurrently to estimate the DNA fragment size. Electrophoresis was carried out in 1 x TBE (Tris, boric acid, EDTA) buffer at 80V for 1 h. The

amplified products on the agarose gel were visualised and snapped using UV light (Alpha Innotech, Biometra).

Antibiotic susceptibility testing

Antibiotic susceptibility testing of the isolates was carried out using the agar disc diffusion method⁴ as recommended by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (2021).⁵ A single typical colony of *Campylobacter jejuni* picked from a blood agar plate was suspended in Muller Hinton broth (Oxoid, UK) and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours microaerobically. The broth culture was diluted to a turbidity equivalent to a 0.5 McFarland standard. The inoculum was then streaked evenly across the entire surface of the Muller Hinton agar using a sterile swab stick. The plates were allowed to dry, and commonly used antibiotic comprising ampicillin (25 µg), tetracycline (25µg), chloramphenicol (30µg), azithromycin (10 µg), gentamicin (10 µg), and ciprofloxacin (5 µg) were placed on the agar surface, The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours under microaerophilic conditions and the zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters using the ruler. The results were interpreted according to Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI) guidelines with zone diameters categorised as susceptible or resistant.¹

Quality Control

C. jejuni (NCTC 1168) and negative controls in each batch of isolations were used as controls. Isolation and confirmation procedures were performed according to standardized protocols. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was used as positive control for oxidase test and *Staphylococcus aureus* as positive control for catalase test.

Ethical Consideration

The study was approved by the Borno State Health Management Board (Reference No: BSHMB 12/05/18). Informed consent was obtained from the parents/caregivers of the participants.

Data analysis

Stata 14.0 software was used for data analysis. Prevalence rates and the differences in prevalence on age and sex distribution as well as the differences in antimicrobial resistance of *C. jejuni* were analysed using percentages.

Results:

A total of 345 children were examined during the period of study, 245 with diarrhoea and 100 without diarrhoea (served as control) (Table 1). Fifty-three with diarrhoea, (53) 21.6% and (5) 5.0% without diarrhoea were positive for *Campylobacter*

jejuni diarrhoeal disease (Table 2). Among the cases, the highest infection rate was in the age group 12-23 months old, accounting for (19) 32.8% of the total patients. The infection was more prevalent in males 30 (24.0%) than in females (23) 19.2% (Table 3). The results of antibiotic susceptibility testing are presented in Table 4. The *C. jejuni* isolates demonstrated high resistance to ampicillin (94.3%), tetracycline (83.0%), and ciprofloxacin (77.4%). In

contrast, the isolates were susceptible to azithromycin (86.8%), gentamicin (90.5%), as well as chloramphenicol (92.5%). Multidrug resistance (MDR, defined as resistance to ≥ 3 antibiotics) was identified in 47 (88.7%) isolates. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) analysis validated 49/53 of the isolates as *C. jejuni* species with a fragment length of 735-base pairs (Fig 1).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the study population

Age (Months)	No. examined (%)	Males (%)	Females (%)
0-5	59	27 (45.7)	32 (54.2)
6-11	44	23 (52.3)	21 (47.7)
12-23	58	31 (53.4)	27 (46.6)
24-35	46	24 (52.2)	22 (47.8)
36-59	38	20 (52.6)	18 (47.4)
Total	245	125 (51.0)	120 (49.0)

Table 2: Sex distribution of patients with *Campylobacter jejuni* enteritis

Category	Number of children examined	No. positive for <i>Cjejuni</i>	Prevalence (%)
Children with diarrhoea			
Male	125	30	24.0
Female	120	23	19.2
Total	245	53	21.6
Children without diarrhoea			
Male	50	4	8.0
Female	50	1	2.0
Total	100	5	5.0

Table 3: Age distribution of patients with *Campylobacter jejuni* enteritis

Age (Months)	No. of Children	No. Positive	Prevalence (%)
0-5	38	8	21.1
6-11	44	11	25.0
12-23	58	19	32.8
24-35	46	8	17.4
36-59	59	7	11.9
Total	245	53	21.6

Table 4: Susceptibility rate of 53 isolates of *C. jejuni* strains to antibiotic agents

Antibiotic	Sensitive strains No.(%)	Resistant strains No. (%)
Ampicillin	3 (5.6)	50 (94.3)
Tetracycline	10 (18.9)	43 (81.1)
Ciprofloxacin	12 (22.6)	41 (77.4)
Azithromycin	46 (86.8)	7 (13.2)
Gentamicin	48 (90.5)	5 (9.4)
Chloramphenicol	49 (92.5)	4 (7.5)

Fig.1: Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR products showing amplicons of *C. jejuni* from diarrhoeic children. Lane M 100 bp ladder as DNA marker: Lanes 1 is positive control for *C. jejuni* while Lane 14 is negative control . Lanes 3 and 12 are positive for *C. jejuni*.

Discussion

The current study reports a prevalence of 21.6% (53/245) for *Campylobacter jejuni* among patients presenting with diarrhoea in Maiduguri, with molecular identification confirming the presence of *C. jejuni* in nearly all the isolates. This result was comparable with previous studies in Nigeria, which reported prevalence rates ranging from 8.2% to 19.1%.^{1,18} The similarities between these studies may be attributed to comparable socioeconomic conditions, environmental factors, and hygiene practices in the study population. In contrast, higher prevalence rates than observed in the current study were reported from Egypt (31.4%)⁷ and Tanzania (31.4%).¹⁰ The observed lower prevalence rate in the current study compared to studies conducted in other African countries may be due to differences in sample collection, storage and transportation procedure, as well as variation in laboratory detection methods. In this study, the prevalence of *Campylobacter jejuni* was higher in cases than in controls, suggesting an association between *Campylobacter* infection and diarrhoea disease. This finding was consistent with the reports of *Campylobacter* as a common cause of gastroenteritis in children from developing countries.^{6,8,13} The highest prevalence of *C. jejuni* was in children aged 12-23 months old. This finding agreed with similar studies that reported maximum

prevalence rates in children below 2 years of age.^{9,14,18} The higher prevalence of *C. jejuni* in toddlers and preschool-age children can be explained by their immature immune function and frequent hand-to-mouth behaviour as well as dependence on others for and hygienic food handling, which make them more susceptible to infection. The finding of the highest occurrence of *Campylobacter* diarrhoea in children under 2 years old in the current study is worrying, since this age group is the most vulnerable to severe consequences of diarrhoeal illness, such as dehydration and malnutrition.^{14,17,21} The higher prevalence of *C. jejuni* in males than females observed in this study was consistent with gender-related prevalence report in Africa^{1,9,12} and Asia.^{15,20} The observed male predominance in *Campylobacter* infection rate, be ascribed to differences in exposure patterns, behaviour factors, cultural practices or hormonal differences. In the current study, antibiotic susceptibility testing results revealed high resistance of our *C. jejuni* isolates to ciprofloxacin, ampicillin, and tetracycline, suggesting that these antibiotics are poor choices for treating *C. jejuni* childhood diarrhoea in Maiduguri. The high susceptibility of the isolates to gentamicin, azithromycin, and chloramphenicol in this study, suggests these antibiotics may be

considered treatment options for *C. jejuni* diarrhoea in Maiduguri children. The patterns of antibiotic susceptibility in the current study differed from reports from previous Nigerian studies, which reported high susceptibility of *Campylobacter* isolates to ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, and tetracycline.^{18,19} Disparities in reported susceptibility results across studies can be due to increasing misuse of antibiotics and bacterial adaptation to antibiotic selection pressure.^{2,22} This finding highlights the need for local antibiotic susceptibility profile of *C. jejuni* isolates in studied area to guide treatment.

The observed high rate of multidrug resistance among *Campylobacter jejuni* in the present study was similar to reports from India,⁸ but incomparable to lower rates reported from Europe.² Multi-drug resistance among *C. jejuni* strains observed in this study is worrying, since it limits antibiotic options for the treatment of campylobacteriosis.

In the current study, PCR confirmed the majority of isolates identified by phenotypic methods as well defined, highlighting the reliability of culture and biochemical test methods employed for the identification of *C. jejuni* species in this study, while the inability to validate some culture-derived isolates by PCR assay suggests a possible mismatch between the primers used in the PCR assay and the target *Campylobacter* gene sequence.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates a high prevalence of *Campylobacter jejuni* diarrhoea, with an alarming resistance to key antibiotics commonly used for treating *Campylobacter* infections in Maiduguri, Nigeria. Clinicians must suspect *Campylobacter* in paediatric patients presenting with diarrhoea in Maiduguri health facilities.

Strengths and weakness of the study

The strength of this study lies in the use of standard microbiological methods, including culture and biochemical reaction methods as well as molecular techniques, which provided a robust and reliable method for accurate identification of *Campylobacter jejuni*. The study limitations included the time-consuming and labor-intensive nature of culture-based methods and potential biases in PCR amplification. Future study should focus on the direct detection of *Campylobacter* in specimens and the determination of antibiotic resistance using molecular diagnosis.

Authors Contributions

AD and GDM conceptualized and designed the study, collected and analyzed data, and drafted the

manuscript. MYS and GDM contributed to the study design and supervised the laboratory analysis. ASB and KA assisted with data collection. GDM, JAA edited the manuscript and JAA, GDM, and MYS provided critical review and final approval of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflicts of interest.

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